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Fiscal Rules and Defence Spending: A Law & Policy Analysis of the European Re-Armament Plan

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Abstract

This article examines the impact of Donald Trump's return to the US presidency on the European economic constitution. In response to new uncertainties in the transatlantic relationship and the ongoing Russian war of aggression in Ukraine, in spring 2025 the EU and its member states loosened fiscal rules and launched a massive defence spending plan. At the European level, the Commission, through ReArmEU, has encouraged the activation of the national escape clause of the Stability and Growth Pact and simultaneously proposed a special fund, SAFE (Security Action for Europe), worth €150 billion. This fund, approved by the Council, will allow states to obtain additional loans to accelerate rearmament. At the national level, Germany, the member state that had traditionally championed fiscal discipline, amended its Basic Law in just one month to authorize unlimited borrowing for defence. These changes have led to a paradigm shift in the functioning of the EMU, away from stability towards recognizing the importance of security. However, the measures taken by the EU and its member states to increase defence spending reveal a series of problems: by relying on national expenditures, they risk creating profound asymmetries among member countries and waste, without achieving a true deterrence capability. Therefore, it would be appropriate for the EU to not simply water down fiscal rules but strengthen its central fiscal capacity by establishing mechanisms for joint financing of a common defence.

Keywords

EU, fiscal rules, defence spending, Trump administration, economic governance

1. Introduction

The return of Donald Trump to the Presidency of the United States (US) has created shockwaves across the globe, upending the equilibria that for eight decades had governed international relations. The new US administration introduced massive reciprocal tariffs on trading partners, including the European Union (EU); questioned traditional alliances, including the role of the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO); and shifted its policy towards the Russian war of aggression against Ukraine. In particular, President Trump opened bilateral diplomatic negotiations with Russia, without involving Ukraine and the EU; and publicly berated Ukrainian President Volodymyr Zelenski, blaming him for starting the war. At the same time, at the Munich Security Conference in February 2025, US Vice President JD Vance accused Europe of undermining democracy, making clear that the US saw the EU as an adversary, rather than a friend.

The purpose of this article is to examine from a law in context perspective how the EU has responded to changes in the transatlantic relationship, exploring specifically the "Trump effect" on Europe's fiscal rules and defence spending. Since the 1992 Maastricht Treaty, which paved the way to the introduction of the euro as a common currency, the EU has been endowed with a thick legal architecture of economic governance, known as Economic and Monetary Union (EMU).¹ EMU is based on a mix between fiscal regulation and fiscal capacity. On the one hand, EMU relies on fiscal rules enshrined both in EU laws, and in national

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¹ Federico Fabbrini, *Economic Governance in Europe* (OUP 2016)

constitutions, that constrain national budgetary policy to avoid negative externalities. On the other hand, since the outburst of the Covid-19 pandemic, the EU has been endowed with a centralized fiscal capacity:² although this fiscal capacity is temporary, it is additional to the fiscal capacity of each of the member states, and is designed to cushion the shocks of a cyclical economic downturn.

The argument of this article is that the return of Donald Trump to the US Presidency had, in less than two months, a dramatic impact on the first prong of the EU's fiscal framework: namely, fiscal regulation. In response to the Trump effect, the EU swiftly moved to hold in abeyance the application of the Stability and Growth Pact (SGP) – the centre-piece of the EU fiscal rules. Specifically, on 4 March 2025 European Commission President Ursula von der Leyen proposed, as part of a so-called ReArmEU plan, to suspend EU fiscal rules to allow member states to massively increase spending on defence, and on 19 March 2025 the European Commission detailed the conditions for accommodating increased defence expenditures within the SGP through the activation of the so-called national escape clause in the SGP.³ These actions will exempt member states from complying with strict EU deficit rules for defence expenditures and make sure that countries that increase defence spending will not be subject to the EU excessive deficit procedure.

At the same time, fiscal rules have also been shelved at the national level, in the EU member state that traditionally championed them most: Germany. In response to changes in transatlantic relations, the CDU/CSU, which emerged victorious in the 23 February 2025 parliamentary elections, quickly struck a deal with the SPD, as well as the Greens, to amend the constitutional balanced budget rule – a signature provision of the German Basic Law which prohibited borrowing. Since the parties of the new *Grosse Koalition*, together with the Greens, did not have a two-third majorities in the newly elected Bundestag, they rushed the constitutional amendment in the outgoing Bundestag, which swiftly approved it on 18 March 2025. Following approval by the Bundesrat on 21 March 2025, the constitutional amendment entered into force on 24 March 2025⁴ – less than a month since the start of the process. Ditching decades of commitment to *Schwarze null*, the constitutional amendment enables Germany, among others, to annually spend over 1% of gross domestic product (GDP) on defence in derogation of the *Schuldebremse*, the constitutional debt brake.

As this article underlines, the fundamental weakening, if not total abandonment, of fiscal regulation at both the EU and the national level – with Germany being the paradigmatic and highly influential case – reveals a paradigm change in the European architecture of fiscal and economic governance, which can only be explained in light of the changing geopolitical context. While traditionally EMU has been founded on a stability paradigm, the latest developments at EU and national level – both designed to increase defence spending and re-armament – reveal the emergence of a new paradigm, based on security. At a time when Russia's war of aggression against Ukraine continues unabated and the security umbrella traditionally provided by the US through NATO is no longer certain, the EU and its member states abandoned their self-imposed fiscal rules to increase public spending on defence, with a view to strengthen their military capabilities, operational readiness and autonomous ability to deter a possible enemy attack.

Nevertheless, as the article claims, the muting of fiscal regulation at EU and national level in response to the changing security context has not yet been accompanied by the emergence of a centralized EU fiscal capacity for defence. On the contrary, the Trump effect on Europe's architecture of fiscal governance has (thus far) not resulted in the emergence of new supranational funding mechanisms akin to the Next Generation EU (NGEU) Recovery Fund the EU established in response to the Covid-19 pandemic. As part of its ReArmEU plan,

² Federico Fabbrini, *EU Fiscal Capacity* (OUP 2022)

³ European Commission communication accommodating increased defence expenditure within the Stability and Growth Pact, 19 March 2025, C(2025) 2000 final.

⁴ Gesetz zur Änderung des Grundgesetzes (Artikel 109, 115 und 143h), BGBl. 2025 I Nr. 94 vom 24.03.2025, available at: <https://www.recht.bund.de/bgbl/1/2025/94/VO.html>

the European Commission proposed, and the Council approved, the creation of a special fund, worth €150bn, which can provide loans to member states who wish to increase their defence investment. This mechanism, known as SAFE (Security Action for Europe), was formally proposed on 19 March 2025, and entered into force in the form of a Council regulation on 27 May 2025. Nevertheless, the legal basis chosen to adopt SAFE, namely Article 122 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU (TFEU), which excludes the European Parliament from decision-making, has led the latter to challenge the legality of the instrument, making its success uncertain. Furthermore, SAFE will only provide loans, not grants, to member states, and its resources will be used to finance national defence forces, not a common EU defence.

In conclusion, by providing a law in context analysis of the major developments that occurred in the EU in spring 2025 – namely the Commission’s ReArmEU plan with the suspension of the SGP and SAFE proposal, and the German constitutional reform of the debt brake – this article sheds light on how changes in transatlantic relations have fundamentally altered the balance between fiscal regulation and fiscal capacity in EMU. While concerns about the end of Pax Americana in Europe has resulted in a fundamental weakening of fiscal regulation, moving EMU from a stability to a security paradigm, the EU has not yet strengthened its centralized fiscal capacity to finance common defence. Yet, this state of affairs risks generating imbalances, as member states have different fiscal space for defence spending, without ensuring any real continental deterrence capabilities. The fragmentation of rearmament at the national level will result in waste rather than real collective capabilities. To avoid this, creative political and legal initiatives will be needed at the European level to establish a supranational common defence financing mechanism.

As such, this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 maps the EU constitutional framework of economic governance, emphasizing the endurance of EU and national fiscal rules and the embryonic emergence of a fiscal capacity in response to Covid-19. Section 3 examines the Trump effect at EU level, analyzing the Commission’s ReArmEU plan, with the suspension of the SGP to accommodate greater defence spending, and the SAFE instrument. Section 4 examines the Trump effect at national level, in Germany, with the constitutional reform of the debt brake. Section 5 underlines how changes at EU and national level in response to Trump fundamentally alter the paradigm of EMU, from stability to security, as the weakening of fiscal regulation will enable greater spending for defence. Nevertheless, Section 6 emphasizes how the weakening of fiscal rules has not been matched by a strengthening of the EU fiscal capacity, highlighting how defence spending remains national, rather than European, and the challenges that this poses. Section 7 finally concludes.

2. The EU constitutional framework of economic governance

As a large body of literature has pointed out, fiscal regulation through binding legal rules has been an essential feature of the EU constitutional architecture of economic governance since its inception with the 1992 Treaty of Maastricht.⁵ Indeed as historian Harold James⁶ pointed out, EMU emerged from a political compromise between France and Germany, which insisted on introducing reference values and procedural requirements for national budgetary policy in order to avoid a transfer union. This was seen as crucial because EMU was not an optimal currency area.⁷ In fact, the transfer of monetary policy to a federal European Central Bank (ECB) coexisted with decentralized economic policies in the several member states. The adoption of a constellation of fiscal rules constraining member states’ budgetary policies was thus regarded as necessary to prevent negative externalities.

⁵ Martin Heipertz and Amy Verdun, *Ruling Europe: The Politics of the Stability and Growth Pact* (CUP 2011)

⁶ Harold James, *The Making of European Monetary Union* (Harvard UP 2012)

⁷ Robert Mundell, “A Theory of Optimal Currency Areas” (1961) 51 *American Economic Review* 657.

Fiscal rules were introduced both at EU and at national level. At EU level, the centrepiece of fiscal regulation is the SGP, initially approved in 1997 and currently enshrined in Protocol No. 12 of the TFEU. The SGP introduces clear numerical rules that member states have to follow in their budgetary policy, namely an obligation to maintain annual deficit below 3% of GDP, and to lower debts below 60% of GDP. EU primary law also introduces a procedure, currently codified in Article 126 TFEU, to correct excessive deficit, which empowers the European Commission to monitor member states' public finances and foresees the possibility to sanction a member state which runs afoul of EU fiscal rules. These rules are then further spelled out in EU secondary legislation, which have detailed procedural mechanisms and specific criteria applicable to member states which are at risk of violating the deficit and debt rule – the so-called preventive arm of the SGP – and states which are already in breach of them – the so-called corrective arm of the SGP.

At national level, instead, fiscal rules emerged later, in response to the euro-crisis that had started in 2008 and took the form of balanced budget constitutional requirements.⁸ The driving force of this process was Germany, which in 2009 amended its Basic Law to introduce a *Schuldebremse*, a debt brake. In response to the deterioration of public finances resulting from the euro-crisis, Germany committed to a fiscal rule even stricter than the one set at EU level. Specifically, Article 109(3) Basic Law was amended to provide that:

“The budgets of the Federation and the Länder shall, in principle, be balanced without revenue from credits. The Federation and Länder may introduce rules intended to take into account, symmetrically in times of upswing and downswing, the effects of market developments that deviate from normal conditions, as well as exceptions for natural disasters or unusual emergency situations beyond governmental control and substantially harmful to the state's financial capacity.”⁹

Furthermore, the same provision, jointly with the amended Article 115 Basic Law, also made clear that the balanced budget requirement for the federal budget “shall be deemed to be satisfied if revenue from credits does not exceed 0.35[% of GDP]”, while tout court prohibiting a deficit to the budget of the Länder.

The German model of constitutionalizing a balance budget requirement did not remain confined to that member state. In response to the euro-crisis, under the leadership of Chancellor Angela Merkel, Germany insisted that other EU member states follow the same template. In fact, the 2012 Treaty on Stability, Coordination and Governance in EMU, known as the Fiscal Compact, compelled precisely that. The core provision of the Fiscal Compact, Article 3, introduced an obligation for contracting parties to constitutionalize a golden rule in their national constitutions.¹⁰ Specifically, Article 3(1)(a) set the general rule that “the budgetary position of the general government of a Contracting Party shall be balanced or in surplus”, with the clarification that this requirement will be considered as respected if deficit does not exceed 0.5% of GDP, save for the possibility to deviate from this convergence path in case of exceptional circumstances. Furthermore, Article 3(2) stated that “[t]he rule set out in paragraph 1 shall take effect in the national law of the Contracting Parties [...] through provisions of binding force and permanent character, preferably constitutional, or otherwise guaranteed to be fully respected and adhered to throughout the national budgetary process.” Describing the Fiscal Compact, Besselink and Reestman¹¹ affirmed that through it “Europe

⁸ Federico Fabbrini et al (eds), *The Constitutionalization of European Budgetary Constraints* (Hart 2014)

⁹ Official English translation of the German Basic Law available here: <https://www.btg-bestellservice.de/pdf/80201000.pdf> (last accessed 22 March 2025)

¹⁰ Federico Fabbrini, “The Fiscal Compact, the ‘Golden Rule’ and the Paradox of European Federalism” (2013) 36 *Boston College International and Comparative Law Review* 1.

¹¹ Leonard Besselink and Jan Herman Reestman, “Editorial: The Fiscal Compact and the European Constitutions: ‘Europe Speaking German’” (2012) 8 *European Constitutional Law Review* 1

was speaking German". In fact, several member states, including Italy, introduced balanced budget requirements in their constitutions.¹²

The cumulative effect of the EU responses first to the euro-crisis, and later in particular to the Covid-19 pandemic, impacted on the overall architecture of European fiscal governance, increasing fiscal integration within EMU.¹³ Yet, the response to the euro-crisis did not lead towards a fiscal capacity.¹⁴ Rather, the EU and its member states tightened fiscal rules, through the Fiscal Compact and a reform of the SGP via the so-called "six pack" and "two pack" legislation. Moreover, the EU and its member states created several bail-out mechanisms, culminating in the establishment of the European Stability Mechanism (ESM) in 2013, to provide financial support to member states in fiscal crises. However, the ESM provided funding to states in fiscal crisis in the form of loans, and subjected these to strict conditionality. In fact, the European Court of Justice (ECJ) in the 2012 *Pringle* case upheld the compatibility of the ESM with the EU Treaties on the ground that "stability support may be granted to ESM Members which are experiencing or are threatened by severe financing problems only when such support is indispensable to safeguard the financial stability of the euro area as a whole and of its Member States and the grant of that support is subject to strict conditionality appropriate to the financial assistance instrument chosen."¹⁵ Consequently, macro-financial assistance programs for indebted countries such as Greece, Ireland, Spain, Portugal and Cyprus were subjected to harsh conditionality, resulting in austerity.¹⁶

In response to Covid-19, by contrast, for the first time ever the EU suspended the fiscal rules of the SGP for three years, from 2020 to 2023, empowering member states to increase public deficit to cushion the economic shock caused by the pandemic.¹⁷ Moreover, the EU established new financial programs – notably a system to support employment re-insurance, known as SURE, and then the Next Generation EU (NGEU) Recovery Fund – which ultimately led to the establishment of a centralized EU fiscal capacity.¹⁸ NGEU in particular, empowers the European Commission to issue €800bn of common debt, and to transfer this to member states to support the post-pandemic economic recovery, with a long term plan to repay the debt with common EU taxes. As such, NGEU vests in the EU new borrowing, spending and prospectively taxing powers. Yet, this fiscal capacity has limitations. On the one hand, SURE operated in the form of back-to-back loans, backed up by national guarantees, which member states had to repay, albeit at favorable terms.¹⁹ On the other hand, NGEU is time-limited as funding was clearly defined as exceptional, and will come to an end in 2026. As Buti and S. Fabbrini²⁰ argued, the time-limited nature of NGEU can be explained by the politics of its approval, and especially Germany's opposition towards a permanent fiscal union.

Furthermore, the pandemic did not bring to an end the "governing by rules and rules by number in the Eurozone."²¹ Following a brief suspension of the SGP during Covid-19 and its immediate aftermath, the EU reintroduced fiscal rules in 2024 and indeed reaffirmed them in a revision of EU secondary legislation approved in April 2024. Through a package of two regulations and a directive, the EU institutions adjusted both the corrective and the preventive arm of the SGP, with the aim to simplify the legal framework and replace the previous one-size-fits-all rules with more tailor-made national pathways to reduce deficit and debt.

¹² See Const. It., Art 81.

¹³ Tomasz Wozniakowski, *Fiscal Unions* (OUP 2022)

¹⁴ Federico Fabbrini, *Economic Governance in Europe* (OUP 2016)

¹⁵ ECJ Case C-370/12 *Pringle*, ECLI:EU:C:2012:756 para 142

¹⁶ Mark Blyth, *Austerity* (OUP 2013)

¹⁷ Antoinio Estella, "The 'Muting' of the Stability and Growth Pact" (2022) *Cambridge Yearbook of European Legal Studies* 1

¹⁸ Federico Fabbrini, *EU Fiscal Capacity* (OUP 2022)

¹⁹ Ian Cooper "Support to Mitigate Unemployment Risks in an Emergency – SURE" in Federico Fabbrini and Christy Ann Petit (eds), *Research Handbook on Post-Pandemic EU Economic Governance and NGEU Law* (Elgar 2024) 80

²⁰ Marco Buti and Sergio Fabbrini, "Next Generation EU and the Future of European Economic Governance: Towards a Paradigm Change or Just a big one-off?" (2023) 30 *Journal of European Public Policy* 676.

²¹ Vivien Schmidt, *Europe's Crisis of Legitimacy* (OUP 2020)

Specifically, regulation (EU) 2024/1263²² on effective coordination of economic policies introduced the key criteria of net expenditure – meaning “government expenditure net of interest expenditure, discretionary revenue measures [...] and one-offs and other temporary measures”²³ – and required member states to lay out medium-term fiscal-structural plans to reduce net expenditure over a 4-year adjustment period, which could be extended to 7 years in case of a relevant set of reforms and investments.²⁴ Yet on the whole, the reformed SGP reaffirmed the importance of fiscal rules.

At the same time, at the national level, taking Germany as the bellwether, the fiscal framework remained largely untouched. In 2022, when the SGP was still temporarily suspended, the Government of Chancellor Olaf Scholz approved through a constitutional revision the creation of a special, one-off 100bn€ fund, financed through debt, to upgrade the German federal army. This measure, which was part of the *Zeitenwende* following Russia’s invasion of Ukraine, however, only marginally impacted on rearmament. Furthermore, efforts to increase public spending were struck down by the German Constitutional Court (BVerfG), on the basis of the *Schuldenbremse*. In particular, in 2023 the BVerfG declared unconstitutional and void Germany’s second supplementary budget act of 2021, which provided for the transfer of an authorization to borrow €60bn, granted in response to the Covid-19 pandemic and not needed in 2021, to the Energy and Climate Fund, since renamed the Climate and Transformation Fund.²⁵ On a legal challenge from the opposition, the BVerfG ruled that the government and the parliamentary majority had violated the constitutional debt break by authorizing additional borrowing for Covid-19 related purposes, but shifting these resources to a different political objective, namely the promotion of climate protection and transformation resulting from the energy crisis caused by Russia’s war in Ukraine. The BVerfG ruling caused a €60bn hole in the government’s budget, and confirmed the unwavering commitment to fiscal rules.²⁶

The return of President Trump for a second term, however, created a real earthquake. As the new US administration openly treated Europe as an adversary, NATO as a burden and Russia as a friend, the EU and its member states were hastily forced to react. This resulted in unprecedented developments in the European constitutional architecture of economic governance, at both the EU and the national levels, to enable massive spending on defence and military rearmament. These will be examined in turn.

3. The Trump effect at EU level: the ReArmEU plan, the suspension of the SGP and the SAFE proposal

While the EU had increased its defence policy to deal with the war in Ukraine,²⁷ the return of Trump to the US presidency pushed EU policy-makers to roll out an unprecedented plan for continental re-armament, based on the suspension of EU fiscal rules. European Commission President Ursula von der Leyen first formally put forward the idea of “unleashing the use of public funding in defence” to ramp up defence spending in a letter sent to heads of state and government on 4 March 2025, ahead of a European Council meeting.²⁸ In this letter, the Commission outlined a plan, subsequently labelled ReArmEU,²⁹ based on five points: namely

²² Regulation (EU) 2024/1263 of the European Parliament and the Council of 29 April 2024 on the effective coordination of economic policies and on the multilateral budgetary surveillance and repealing Council regulation (EC) No 1466/97.

²³ Ibid art 2(2)

²⁴ Lucio Pench, “The New Stability and Growth Pact: Innovation and Continuity in the Light of NextGenerationEU”, Federico Fabbrini and Christy Ann Petit (eds), *Research Handbook on Post-Pandemic EU Economic Governance and NGEU Law* (Elgar 2024) 299

²⁵ BVerfG, 2 BvF 1/22, Judgment of 15 November 2023.

²⁶ See also Financial Times editorial, “Germany’s overzealous debt brake”, 28 November 2023.

²⁷ Federico Fabbrini, *The EU Constitution in Time of War* (OUP 2025)

²⁸ European Commission President, Letter, Brussels 4 March 2025, p 3

²⁹ European Commission President, Speech at European Parliament, Strasbourg, 11 March 2025, SPEECH/25/739.

(1) the activation of the SGP escape clause to enable greater national spending on defence; (2) the creation of a special €150bn fund to provide loans to member states to ramp up defence expenditures; (3) the possibility to re-allocate cohesion policy funding for defence; (4) the expansion of the European Investment Bank (EIB)'s mandate on defence; and (5) the mobilization of private capital. The European Council on 6 March 2025 endorsed the Commission proposal, inviting it also to explore additional sources of common funding,³⁰ and the European Parliament also welcome it in a non-binding resolution adopted on 12 March 2025.³¹

While points 3, 4 and 5, of the Commission ReArmEU plan will need to be further worked out, including by the EIB, on 19 March 2025 the European Commission jointly with the EU High Representative unveiled a White paper on European defence readiness.³² In conjunction with this, the Commission released a communication on accommodating increased defence expenditure within the SGP, detailing the first point of the ReArmEU plan.³³ Moreover, the Commission also published a proposal for a Council regulation establishing a special 150bn€ fund to provide loans to Member States to ramp up defence expenditure, known as SAFE (Security Action for Europe), thus advancing a legislative text to operationalize the second point of the ReArmEU plan.³⁴

The Commission communication on accommodating increased defence expenditure within the SGP, which is only 7 pages long, begins by stating that “[i]n a context of heightened geopolitical tensions [...] Europe must urgently step up its defence capabilities” and acknowledges that this “require[s] an urgent increase in European defence spending.”³⁵ Consequently, the communication affirms that the impact of “higher level of defence expenditure on Member States’ budgets can be accommodated [...] through the flexibility provided within the existing EU fiscal framework.”³⁶ Specifically, “in view of the extraordinary situation, the Commission proposes to unlock additional flexibility for higher defence spending through a coordinated activation of the national escape clause”³⁷ enshrined in Article 26 of regulation (EU) 2024/1263,³⁸ the preventive arm of the SGP. This provision empowers the Council, acting by qualified majority voting, following a request from a member state and a recommendation by the Commission, to allow a member state to deviate from its net expenditure path “where exceptional circumstances outside the control of the Member State have a major impact on the public finances of the Member States concerned.”

According to the Commission, circumstances allow for triggering the national escape clause, thus enabling up to €650bn of national spending on defence, as indicated by President von der Leyen in her ReArmEU plan. In the communication on accommodating increased defence expenditure within the SGP, therefore, the Commission calls on “all Member States” to make use of the flexibility activating their national escape clause “in a coordinated manner”³⁹ and invites national governments “to come forward with the request to activate the national escape clause by the end of April [2025].”⁴⁰ As the Commission makes clear, the activation of the national escape clause allows member states to deviate from the net expenditure path, which as mentioned above requires member states to lower their deficit in

³⁰ European Council Conclusions, 6 March 2025, EUCO 6/25, para 6a).

³¹ European Parliament resolution of 12 March 2025 on the white paper on the future of European defence, P10_TA(2025)0034, para 76

³² European Commission & High Representative joint White paper for European defence readiness 2030, 19 March 2025, JOIN(2025) 120 final

³³ European Commission communication accommodating increased defence expenditure within the Stability and Growth Pact, 19 March 2025, C(2025) 2000 final.

³⁴ European Commission proposal for a Council regulation establishing the Security Action for Europe (SAFE) through the reinforcement of European defence industry instrument, 19 March 2025, COM(2025) 122 final

³⁵ C(2025) 2000 final, p.1

³⁶ Ibid

³⁷ Ibid, p.2

³⁸ Regulation (EU) 2024/1263 of the European Parliament and the Council of 29 April 2024 on the effective coordination of economic policies and on the multilateral budgetary surveillance and repealing Council regulation (EC) No 1466/97.

³⁹ Ibid

⁴⁰ Ibid, p.7

the medium term. This means that member states will be legally authorized to indebted themselves to a much greater degree. Furthermore, the activation of the national escape clause means that a member state breaching the SGP criteria, with a deficit over 3% of GDP, will not be subjected to the excessive deficit procedure.

At the same time, in its communication the Commission endeavors to delimit the flexibility for higher defence expenditure. First, in terms of scope, the communication states that “the flexibility would cover the increase of total defence expenditure, including both investment and current expenditure.”⁴¹ Specifically the Commission defines which statistical category of public expenditure falls under the exception, using a classification which is close to that used by NATO to measure defence expenditure. Second, in terms of size, the communication states that the flexibility under the national escape clause “should be capped at 1.5% of GDP, compared to the net expenditure path” of each member state, with the aim to secure fiscal sustainability.⁴² Third, in terms of duration, the communication foresees that the activation of the national escape clause for defence expenditure will be available initially “for a period of four years, starting in 2025.”⁴³ Yet the communication affirms that the reference year to calculate increase in defence expenditure will retroactively be 2021, so as to reward “Member States that have already ramped up their defence spending since the start of Russia’s war of aggression against Ukraine.”⁴⁴

Also on 19 March 2025, the Commission proposed a Council regulation establishing a special €150bn fund: SAFE. This instrument is based on Article 122 TFEU, which allows the Council to “decide, in a spirit of solidarity between Member States, upon the measures appropriate to the economic situation” and to provide financial assistance to a member state in case, among others, of “exceptional occurrences beyond its control”. Article 122 TFEU has been used as the legal basis for the adoption of various economic policy measures, including SURE and NGEU,⁴⁵ and regulations adopted under this legal basis are approved by qualified majority voting in the Council. The aim of SAFE is to accelerate re-armament by the member states providing EU financial support in the form of loans to ramp up defence industrial production. At the same time, SAFE endeavors to tackle the notorious fragmentation of the EU defence market – with its dysfunctional segmentation along national lines – by incentivizing joint procurement, and indeed SAFE conditions the disbursement of loans to member states acting together. The Council quickly considered the Commission’s proposal and approved it, with some amendments, in less than two months. The SAFE Regulation thus entered into force on 27 May 2025.

Pursuant to Article 1, the Council regulation establishes SAFE and sets out conditions and procedures under which the financial assistance shall be provided to and implemented by the Member States. In terms of objective, SAFE is designed to provide funding for the procurement of key military capabilities, including ammunitions and missiles, artillery systems, drones, air and missile defence and strategic enablers. As specified in Article 2(3), to access SAFE funding Member States must proceed with “joint procurement”: a Member State can request support provided it uses the funds to purchase military capabilities jointly with another EU Member State, Ukraine or third countries “with whom the Union has entered a Security and Defence Partnership”. Article 17 further details the conditions for third country participation into the program. On the other hand, Article 16 provides that the value of the contract shall not include material produced outside the EU for a percentage exceeding 35%. However, compared to the original Commission proposal, the Council insisted on introducing an exception to joint purchasing: pursuant to Article 4(3), in fact, Member States are also allowed to individually and unilaterally proceed with autonomous purchasing for a whole year, until 30 May 2026, in derogation from the joint purchasing rule.

⁴¹ Ibid, p.4

⁴² Ibid, p.5

⁴³ Ibid, p.6

⁴⁴ Ibid.

⁴⁵ Bruno De Witte, “The European Union’s Covid-19 Recovery Plan: The Legal Engineering of an Economic Policy Shift” (2012) 58 *Common Market Law Review* 635.

From a funding perspective, Article 9 of the regulation enables the Commission to borrow funds on the financial markets, but as clearly indicated in Article 5 this is up to a maximum of €150bn. From a governance perspective, SAFE follows the legal technology of NGEU.⁴⁶ According to Article 7 of the regulation, member states have to present a “European defence industry investment plan”, with the description of the defence products need, and the description of the planned activities to ramp up defence production. As indicated in Article 12, member states can request loan financing to the Commission “until 31 December 2030.” Pursuant to Article 8, the Commission “shall assess” national plans, and decide on the request for financial assistance. Once the national plan has been assessed positively, as indicated in Article 10, the Commission and member states will enter into a loan agreement and operational arrangements, and pursuant to Article 11 the Commission can disburse to the relevant member state a pre-financing payment. However, as indicated in Article 12, the Commission will regularly monitor advancement with the implementation of the national defence plan, authorizing the disbursement of periodic installments only if there has been progress in the implementation of national investment plans in the defence industry, which, pursuant to Article 18, may also include changes to existing contracts or framework agreements. SAFE, finally, introduces regular monitoring,⁴⁷ reporting⁴⁸ and communication⁴⁹ requirements, with the application of rules on classified and sensitive information.⁵⁰

The Commission’s *ReArmEU* plan represents a turning point in EU fiscal governance. The Commission’s decision to introduce a derogation from the SGP to encourage national defence spending effectively suspends European fiscal rules, allowing for greater defence investment. At the same time, with SAFE, the Commission and the Council have established a new financial instrument to provide additional support to Member States, in the form of loans of up to €150 billion, to increase joint military procurement (at least after an initial transition year). Despite the limitations discussed below, SAFE and the immediate activation of national safeguard clauses in the SGP have significant implications for the constitutional architecture of European economic governance, recognizing that security comes at a high cost and thus allowing for greater spending to pursue this essential public good.

4. The Trump effect at national level: the amendment of the constitutional debt brake in Germany

While the Trump effect prompted the EU to overhaul its fiscal framework, important developments have occurred as a result of changes to transatlantic relations also at the national level, especially in Germany. In late November 2024, the three-party coalition between SPD, the Greens and the FDP collapsed – aptly, as a result of a dispute over the next budget. In snap elections held on 23 February 2025, the CDU/CSU under the leadership of Friedrich Merz won the most votes and immediately entered into negotiations with the SPD to form a *Grosse Koalition*. Reacting to the action of the Trump administration, however, the two parties quickly reneged on pledges made during the electoral campaign and agreed to amend the constitutional balanced budget obligation in order to increase spending on defence and investment on infrastructure and domestic industry. At the same time, since the CDU/CSU and the SPD did not have in the newly elected Bundestag the 2/3 majority required to approve a constitutional amendment, they decided to use the outgoing Parliament, which was formally in office until 23 March 2025, to modify the *Schuldenbremse*. While this decision raised the issue of legitimacy, it stood from the point of view of legality. In fact, the BVerfG

⁴⁶ Federico Fabbrini, “NGEU as a New Legal Technology of European Governance” (2024) 47 *Journal of European Integration* 85

⁴⁷ SAFE art.14

⁴⁸ Ibid art.15

⁴⁹ Ibid art.22

⁵⁰ Ibid art.21

rejected as inadmissible the constitutional complaint raised by opposition party AfD which tried to suspend the convocation of the Bundestag.

Consequently the German Parliament was summoned for a special session, and thanks to a cross-party agreement reached between the CDU/CSU, the SPD and the Greens, which set aside additional funding for climate transition, on 18 March 2025 the Bundestag approved by a majority of 513-to-207 (with 0 abstentions) the revision of the Basic Law. (The Bundestag had 733 members and a constitutional revision required a two-third majority, hence 489 votes). Subsequently, on 21 March 2025, the Bundesrat – the upper chamber of the German legislature, which represents the 16 federal Länder – also approved with a 53-to-16 majority (with an abstention counting as a negative vote) the constitutional revision (The Bundesrat has 69 votes and a constitutional revision required a two-third majority, hence 46 votes). Following the signature by the federal President Frank-Walter Steinmeier and its publication on the Bundesgesetzblatt (official gazette) on 24 March 2025,⁵¹ the groundbreaking constitutional reform entered into force – just a month and a day after the Bundestag election.

Specifically, the German constitutional revision introduced a new sentence in Article 109(3) Basic Law, and amended with identical words also Article 115(2) Basic Law, stating that “The amount by which defence expenditures exceed 1 percent of nominal gross domestic product shall be deducted from the income from loans to be taken into account.”⁵² This effectively allows the German federal government to indebt itself over 1% of GDP on defence expenditure outside the restriction of the debt brake, which as mentioned above constrained the deficit to 0.35% of GDP. Furthermore – reflecting the political compromise between the CDU/CSU, which pushed for greater spending on defence, and the SPD and the Greens, which pushed for greater spending on social policy and the climate transition – the constitutional reform introduced in the Basic Law a new Article 143h, which enabled “the Federation [to] establish a special fund with its own borrowing authority for investments in infrastructure with a volume of up to €500 billion”⁵³, outside the constraints of the *Schuldebremse*, of which €100bn will be allocated to the Länder. Finally – in a political move designed to secure the support of the Bundesrat for the constitutional amendment – the revision empowered the Länder to also run annual deficits up to 0.35% of GDP, like the federal government.

Germany’s approval of the constitutional reform of the debt brake has been dubbed by the new Chancellor Friedrich Merz as a “whatever it takes moment” – in a clear reference to the speech that then ECB President Mario Draghi gave in 2012, and which proved to be essential to the preservation of EMU during the euro-crisis. In particular, by exempting any defence spending over and above 1% of GDP from the debt brake, the constitutional reform effectively permits Germany to indefinitely borrow to strengthen its defence – with early estimates suggesting that the country may invest €1tn on defence within a decade. This open-ended exemption fundamentally weakens the logic of the *Schuldenbremse*, which is formally preserved in the Basic Law but practically emasculated. Furthermore, since defence spending traditionally drives economic growth, with impact on industrial policy and employment, the reform injects a Keynesian turn into the German economic model. As pointed out by Deutsche Bank, “this is one of the most historic paradigm shifts in German postwar history. Both the speed at which this is happening and the magnitude of the prospective fiscal expansion is reminiscent of German reunification.”⁵⁴

⁵¹ Gesetz zur Änderung des Grundgesetzes (Artikel 109, 115 und 143h), BGBl. 2025 I Nr. 94 vom 24.03.2025, available at: <https://www.recht.bund.de/bgbl/1/2025/94/VO.html>

⁵² My translation. Original in German: „Von den zu berücksichtigenden Einnahmen aus Krediten ist der Betrag abzuziehen, um den die Verteidigungsausgaben 1 vom Hundert im Verhältnis zum nominalen Bruttoinlandsprodukt übersteigen.“

⁵³ My translation. Original in German: „Der Bund kann ein Sondervermögen mit eigener Kreditermächtigung für Investitionen in die Infrastruktur mit einem Volumen von bis zu 500 Milliarden Euro errichten.“

⁵⁴ “A Historic ‘Whatever it takes’ Moment”, Deutsche Bank Research, 4 March 2025

5. From stability to security

A law in context analysis reveals how the developments occurred at EU and national level since the return of Donald Trump to the US Presidency have fundamentally transformed – in a few months – the EU legal framework of economic governance. Traditionally, the European architecture of economic and fiscal governance as created by the 1992 Maastricht Treaty has been based on a paradigm of stability. In fact, in its 1993 *Maastricht Urteil*, the German BVerfG upheld the constitutionality of the Maastricht Treaty on the grounds that it created a stability union.⁵⁵ Furthermore the concern for stability was at the heart of the response to the euro-crisis – as evidence by the adoption of the Fiscal Compact, and indeed the reform of the SGP. Moreover, also the EU response to Covid-19 did not fundamentally challenge the stability paradigm of EMU: while the EU temporarily suspended the SGP, and created an ad hoc centralized fiscal capacity through NGEU, it confirmed the centrality of fiscal rules designed to constrain national budgetary policy by reforming the SGP in 2023-4.

On the contrary, security concerns were largely absent from the operation of EMU. In 2014, when Russia illegally seized Crimea, NATO, under the leadership of then US President Barack Obama, had requested European allies to increase defence spending to at least 2% of GDP.⁵⁶ Moreover, during his first term, President Trump had made clear that he expected NATO European allies to share the burden of their defence, and questioned the mutual defence pledge at the heart of the transatlantic alliance. Nevertheless – even though from a legal viewpoint NATO requirements should have trumped EU budgetary constraints⁵⁷ – EU member states systematically failed to increase their defence spending. Russia's large scale invasion of Ukraine in 2022 – with the return of conventional warfare on the European continent on a scale unseen since World War II – eventually led to a slow but steady increase of national funding for defence. Yet Russia's war of aggression against Ukraine did not fundamentally alter the stability paradigm of the EU fiscal framework. At the EU level, the issue hardly emerged in the SGP revision process, in 2023-4, and despite calls in this direction, the preventive arm of the new SGP limited itself to referring to "where necessary, the build-up of defence capabilities" as one of the elements to be included in national mid-term fiscal-structural plans.⁵⁸

Action taken at EU and national level in the first two months of the second Trump presidency, however, have fundamentally changed the paradigm of EU economic governance, with security coming front and center as the core objective of fiscal policy. At EU level, the Commission has for all practical purposes suspended the application of the SGP, while envisioning also a special fund named SAFE to support the national ramp-up of defence production, which was swiftly approved by the Council. At the national level, in Germany, a "fiscal revolution"⁵⁹ has occurred in less than a month with the Parliament emasculating the constitutional debt brake to effectively enable unlimited borrowing for defence. The combined effect of this development is that for the first time since its establishment EMU is no longer subject to strict fiscal rules. Indeed, during Covid-19 and its aftermath the SGP was temporarily suspended, but fiscal rules still remained in place at national level – as the nullification of the German budget act for 2023 proved. Now, Germany, the largest EU member states – and hitherto the champion of fiscal regulation – has freed itself from fiscal rules, opening a path that other member states will follow with the EU's blessing.

This paradigmatic change in the legal framework can only be explained as a result of fundamental shifts in the geopolitical context and the transatlantic relationship. In its March 2025 communication on accommodating increased defence spending within the SGP the Commission stated that "Russia's war of aggression against Ukraine and its threat to

⁵⁵ BVerfG 89, 155 (1993)

⁵⁶ NATO Wales Summit Declaration 4 July 2022.

⁵⁷ Federico Fabbrini, "Do NATO Obligations Trump European Budgetary Constraints?" (2018) 9 *Harvard National Security Journal* 121.

⁵⁸ Regulation 2024/1263 art 13(c)(iv)

⁵⁹ Peter Bofinger, "Germany Ditches Debt Brake – A Fiscal Revolution Begins", *Social Europe*, 21 March 2025

European security are exceptional circumstances outside the control of Member States, which have a major impact on Member States' public finances through the related incurred and/or planned increase in defence expenditure."⁶⁰ But this is an improbable and unconvincing justification for activating the escape clause in the SGP. Russia's large scale invasion of Ukraine had started three years before, in February 2022. In fact, Russia's had already illegally seized Crimea in February 2014. The real change that explains why the Commission now activates the SGP escape clause is the return of Donald Trump to the US Presidency, and the fundamental unraveling of the transatlantic relationship. From this point of view, German Chancellor Merz has been more honest in explaining why the German constitutional debt brake had to go: at a time when America can no longer be taken for granted, Europe had to step up, including by providing for its own defence.

In conclusion, the abandonment of the stability paradigm in favor of a security one confirms that a balanced-budget policy is not compatible with having an army. Historically, nation states have used debt to finance standing armies, with which to wage war and ensure peace.⁶¹ It is no coincidence that the US, which for over seven decades has guaranteed security in Europe and the world, does not have a balanced budget requirement in its federal constitution and has regularly had a spending deficit, precisely to finance the most powerful army in the world. But in their illusion of "perpetual peace" Germany and Europe had believed they could focus only on the *Schwarze null*, ignoring their security. With Trump, Europe and Germany have now woken up to the dark reality of hard power, and transformed in few months the EU architecture of fiscal governance to deal with defence needs, re-armament and strategic autonomy.

6. Problems and Prospects

While the measures adopted at the European and national levels in response to Trump's re-election address a real need—that of increasing European defence at a time when the US commitment towards the Old Continent's security can no longer be taken for granted—they nonetheless raise a series of problems. As previously explained, the changes introduced to European and national fiscal rules are essentially aimed at enabling greater defence spending by member states. The activation of the national safeguard clause of the SGP, as well as the removal of the balanced budget rule in the German Basic Law, will allow for an increase in national defence spending. On the other hand, the SAFE instrument itself allows member states who wish to request EU loans to increase their defence spending—and although in principle the €150 billion SAFE fund must be spent on joint procurement, an exemption clause in the Council regulation actually allows states to proceed with individual procurement until 30 May 2026.

However, the ability of EU member states to increase their defence deficits is profoundly unequal. In particular, high-debt member states will still be limited by financial markets, though no longer by fiscal rules, in their ability to increase spending. As Daniel Kelemen and Terence Teo pointed out, fiscal rules have never been the true constraint on states' budgetary policy: rather, they have acted as reference points for the financial markets, which increased the cost of debt for countries that did not meet their fiscal targets.⁶² This market pressure will not abate now that EU or national fiscal rules have been silenced. It is no coincidence that as of April 30, 2025, the deadline indicated by the European Commission as the cut-off moment to request the activation of the national safeguard clause of the SGP, only 16 EU member states have invoked this option.⁶³ While this number represents the majority of

⁶⁰ C(2025) 2000 final, p.2

⁶¹ Charles Tilly (ed), *The Formation of National States in Western Europe* (Princeton University Press, 1975) (famously stating that war makes states and states make war).

⁶² Daniel Kelemen – Terence Teo, "Law, Focal Points and Fiscal Discipline in the European Union and the United States" (2014) *American Political Science Review*.

⁶³ Council of the EU, press release, "Coordinated Activation of the National Escape Clause", 30 April 2025, 307/25.

EU member states (currently 27), it is significant that it excludes three of the four largest EU member states: France, Italy, and Spain. In other words, with the exception of Germany—whose defence spending increase is facilitated by the very low rate of financing on financial markets—only small or medium-sized EU member states—primarily in Eastern and Northern Europe, where the Russian threat is most pronounced—have invoked the option to suspend the SGP provided for by the ReArmEU program.

This also raises another problematic aspect of the rearmament program launched by the European Commission together with the Member States: the uncertainty about its real effectiveness. Since the increase in defence spending is occurring on a national basis, it is far from clear that it will result in greater European military capabilities, and therefore credible deterrence from external threats. If the objective of ReArmEU is to replace US military power with European autonomous capabilities, it seems unrealistic this can be achieved through a simple increase in defence spending—even to the 5% of GDP (of which 3.5% is pure military spending and 1.5% dedicated to technology and infrastructure) envisaged at the recent NATO summit of 25 June 2025⁶⁴—by 27 small nation states. Indeed, the risk is that this increased spending will result in unnecessary national duplication and waste, worsening the already harmful fragmentation of the European defence market.⁶⁵ While Germany will certainly be able to create the most powerful European army thanks to its size and economic strength—as Chancellor Merz stated with surprising *nonchalance*⁶⁶—it is clear that increased spending by the other 15 member states that have invoked the national escape clause of the SGP—namely, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czechia, Denmark, Estonia, Greece, Croatia, Lithuania, Latvia, Hungary, Poland, Portugal, Slovenia, Slovakia, and Finland—will not in and of itself generate an effective EU deterrence power.

Otherwise, the same financial obstacles that have discouraged several member states from requesting the activation of the SGP's national safeguard clause also hinder the success of SAFE. This instrument, in fact, relies on loans—like SURE (the unemployment benefit mechanism created during the pandemic)—but not on subsidies—like NGEU. The loans contracted by member states with the European Commission impact their national debt, and therefore also their financial rating. For this reason, more than a month after the approval of the SAFE regulation, no Member State has yet submitted a request for funding, and the EU expects that a large share of the €150 billion SAFE fund will most likely remain untapped. Furthermore, as mentioned above, the European Parliament has filed an action for annulment against the SAFE regulation before the ECJ, challenging the legal basis used to create the instrument.⁶⁷ Article 122 TFEU, in fact, excludes the European Parliament from the decision-making process, which relies exclusively on the Council. This state of affairs raises clear democratic problems and clashes with the position that the President of the European Commission took before the European Parliament ahead of her re-election in July 2024: on that occasion, Von der Leyen had promised to resort to legislative acts pursuant to Article 122 TFEU only in exceptional cases.⁶⁸ Practice, however, has been quite different.⁶⁹ It is therefore not implausible that the ECJ will subject SAFE to rigorous constitutional review.

In light of all this, it would be appropriate for the EU to move beyond the *ReArmEU* program by establishing mechanisms for common financing of the common defence. Instead of simply allowing for an increase in national defence spending by relaxing fiscal rules, the

⁶⁴ NATO The Hague Summit Declaration, 25 June 2025.

⁶⁵ See already Bianca Ballester, “The Cost of Non-Europe in Common Security and Defence Policy”, EPRS, European Parliament, 2013.

⁶⁶ See German Federal Government, First government statement: “Responsibility for Germany”, 14 May 2025, disponibile a: <https://www.bundesregierung.de/breg-en/news/first-government-statement-chancellor-merz-2347710>

⁶⁷ <https://www.euronews.com/my-europe/2025/06/25/meps-vote-for-parliament-to-sue-commission-over-150bn-defence-loan-programme>

⁶⁸ European Commission President-elect Ursula von der Leyen, “Europe’s Choice : Political Guidelines for the next European Commission 2024-2029”, 18 July 2024, 30.

⁶⁹ Merijn Chamón, The Use of Article 122 TFEU: Institutional Implications and Impact on Democratic Accountability, report commissioned by the European Parliament Constitutional Affairs Committee, September 2023, 41.

European legal architecture of economic governance should be enriched with a new centralized fiscal capacity, modeled on NGEU, but dedicated to defence spending. This was, actually, the model of the European Defence Community (EDC), established by a treaty in 1952, which as I have explained elsewhere could be revived today.⁷⁰ The EDC would have, among other things, integrated the armed forces of the member states (the six founding countries) into a common army, financed by a common budget and governed by supranational institutions (largely corresponding to those of the EU institutions today).⁷¹ While under the pressure of a changing geopolitical context *ReArmEU* modified the European constitutional framework of economic governance by removing fiscal rules, the EDC offered what Europe lacks—and needs—today: a central fiscal capacity to finance a collective defence that is credible in terms of deterrence.

7. Conclusion

Trump's return to the US presidency has had an unprecedented impact on Europe's constitutional framework of economic governance. In response to new uncertainties in the transatlantic relationship and Russia's ongoing war of aggression in Ukraine, the EU and its member states have loosened fiscal rules limiting debt and launched a massive defence spending plan. At the European level, the Commission, through *ReArmEU*, has encouraged the activation of the national escape clause of the SGP and simultaneously proposed a special fund, SAFE, worth €150 billion, which was approved by the Council and will allow states who wish to obtain additional loans to accelerate rearmament. At the national level, Germany, the member state that had traditionally championed fiscal discipline, amended its Basic Law in just one month to authorize unlimited defence borrowing. These changes led to a shift in the paradigm underpinning the functioning of EMU – away from stability, towards the recognition of the importance of security. However, the measures taken by the EU and its member states to increase defence spending reveal a series of problems: by relying on national expenditures, they risk creating profound asymmetries among member states and waste, without achieving a real deterrence capability. Therefore, it would be appropriate for the EU to not simply water down fiscal rules but rather strengthen its central fiscal capacity by establishing mechanisms for common financing of a common defence.

⁷⁰ Federico Fabbrini, "European Defence Integration after Trump: A Proposal to Revive the European Defence Community Treaty and its Legal Feasibility" (2024) 30 *European Law Journal* 614.

⁷¹ For a policy proposal to relaunch the EDC see the ALCIDE project I founded: www.alcideproject.eu

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